

07-013 – AI agent for calculating screening variables in collusion detection – Agente de inteligencia artificial para el cálculo de variables de cribado en la detección de colusión

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Collusion in procurement is an unlawful practice in which competing firms secretly coordinate their bid prices, undermining market competition. A persistent challenge for contracting authorities is the difficulty in detecting non-competitive bids, which frequently leads to the awarding of contracts at inflated prices. Screening Variables are specific indices derived from the distribution of bid values in each auction (i.e., the prices offered by bidders). These indices facilitate the processing of auction data by machine learning algorithms, enhancing their capacity to identify collusive behavior. Screening variables are instrumental not only in flagging potential collusion within individual auctions but also in detecting sustained collusive patterns among specific bidders. Typically, these variables consist of statistical indices computed directly from bid values in each procurement process. Although their computation is generally straightforward, a proper understanding of the underlying terminology is required, particularly for public officials involved in decision-making during the contract award process. This study presents the development of an artificial intelligence agent, integrated into a chatbot, designed to assist in the calculation of screening variables, thereby supporting more effective detection of collusive practices.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Collusion; Agent; Chatbot; Screening variables*

La colusión en contratación es un fenómeno ilegal en el que empresas competidoras pactan los precios de sus ofertas, perjudicando la competencia del mercado. Uno de los desafíos recurrentes para las autoridades contratantes es la dificultad para identificar ofertas no competitivas, lo que frecuentemente resulta en la adjudicación de contratos a precios inflados. Las Variables de Cribado son índices específicos derivados de la distribución de los valores de las ofertas en cada subasta (precios ofrecidos por los licitadores). Estas variables pueden ayudar a los algoritmos de aprendizaje automático a procesar la información de las subastas de manera más eficiente para detectar colusión. Las variables de cribado no solo son útiles para señalar una posible colusión en una subasta determinada, sino también para identificar patrones colusorios sostenidos entre ciertos licitadores. Habitualmente, estas variables consisten en índices estadísticos calculados directamente a partir de los valores de las ofertas. Aunque no son difíciles de calcular, requieren de cierto dominio de la nomenclatura por parte de quien las calcule, por ejemplo, un funcionario público que participe en la toma de decisiones. La comunicación describe el desarrollo de un agente de inteligencia artificial que, integrado en un chatbot, asiste al cálculo de las variables.

Palabras claves: *Inteligencia Artificial; Colusión; Agente; Chatbot; Variables de cribado*

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1. Introduction

Public procurement represents one of the fundamental pillars in the functioning of public administrations, as it channels a significant portion of state spending towards goods, services, and works of collective interest. Within this framework, public tenders are complex procedures through which contracts are awarded to companies via open competitions. These processes are governed by strict regulations that require transparency, equal treatment, and efficiency, which implies careful management of large volumes of technical, legal, and administrative documentation.

Ensuring fair competitiveness in public tenders is a cornerstone of transparent and efficient public procurement. It fosters equal opportunities for all potential suppliers, thereby enhancing innovation, improving quality, and reducing costs through genuine market competition. A competitive and impartial bidding process not only prevents favoritism and corruption but also strengthens public trust in governmental institutions. Moreover, it facilitates the optimal allocation of public resources by allowing administrations to select the most economically advantageous offers. Consequently, maintaining fair competitiveness in public tenders is essential for promoting accountability, safeguarding the public interest, and upholding the principles of good governance.

Collusion in public procurement undermines the integrity and efficiency of the tendering process, leading to inflated prices, reduced quality of goods and services, and significant losses for public administrations. When suppliers engage in anti-competitive practices—such as bid rigging, market allocation, or price fixing—they distort the competitive environment, effectively nullifying the benefits of open and fair competition. Such practices not only burden public budgets but also erode public confidence in the procurement system. Furthermore, collusion diminishes incentives for innovation and efficiency among suppliers, ultimately harming economic growth and public welfare. Detecting and preventing collusion is therefore crucial to ensuring value for money and preserving the legitimacy of public procurement systems.

The use of screening variables has emerged as a valuable tool in the detection of collusion in public tenders, providing empirical indicators that help identify suspicious bidding patterns. These variables, often derived from bid data, include measures such as the bid dispersion, frequency of winning by specific firms, rotation of winners, and anomalies in bid timing or pricing behavior. By systematically analyzing these indicators, procurement authorities and competition agencies can flag potential instances of collusion for further investigation. While screening methods do not constitute definitive proof, they significantly enhance the capacity to monitor procurement processes proactively and cost-effectively. Incorporating such tools into routine oversight mechanisms contributes to the deterrence of anti-competitive behavior and supports the broader objective of safeguarding the integrity of public procurement systems.

Although the computation of screening variables is typically straightforward from a technical standpoint, their effective application demands a solid understanding of the underlying economic and statistical concepts. This is especially important for public officials who are directly involved in evaluating bids and making decisions during the contract award process. A lack of familiarity with key terminology and interpretative nuances can lead to misjudgment or oversight of potential red flags, thereby weakening the early detection of collusive behavior. Therefore, integrating chatbot-based assistance into procurement workflows can enhance the effective use of screening variables by guiding public officers through their calculation and interpretation, reducing the risk of misapplication and promoting more informed, data-driven decision-making in the detection of collusive practices.

Recent advancements in chatbot technologies powered by generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) have significantly expanded their potential applications in complex administrative tasks, including public procurement oversight. Unlike earlier rule-based systems, Gen AI-driven chatbots can understand and generate natural language, interpret nuanced queries, and provide context-aware explanations. This progress enables them to support public officers not only in performing routine calculations—such as computing screening variables—but also in interpreting results, identifying anomalies, and suggesting follow-up actions. By combining data-driven analysis with conversational interfaces, these tools can democratize access to technical knowledge, streamline procurement procedures, and ultimately contribute to more transparent and accountable decision-making processes.

Recent literature supports this innovative application. For example, Datcu & Maathuis have introduced LLMs-based (Large Languages Models) systems trained on legal corpora that assist experts in interpreting complex procurement regulations, increasing accuracy and reducing errors in decision-making (Datcu & Maathuis, 2024). Other studies have illustrated the use of natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract useful information from tender documents, contracts, and heterogeneous databases, presenting it accessibly through semantic search engines, automatic summaries, and interactive dashboards (Siciliani et al., 2023). These tools enable more agile document management and greater traceability in decisions made throughout the procurement lifecycle. Beyond textual analysis, LLMs are integrated within broader automation systems that examine massive datasets related to public procurement processes. A notable example is “BRAVA” (Bid Rigging Algorithm for Vigilance in Antitrust), a tool developed by the Economic Intelligence Unit (UIE) of the Competition Directorate of the CNMC (Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia), Spain’s competition authority (CNMC Blog, 2024). Other example is “Alice”, the AI system developed by the Office of the Comptroller General of Brazil, designed to cross-reference information from multiple sources to detect risks in tenders, reducing audit times from over a year to just a few days (Menke et al., 2024).

This paper focuses on the development of an intelligent agent that leverages the capabilities of an LLM integrated in a chatbot to assist and automate the computation of a set of screening variables with a public tender. An LLM is extended by means of a toolbox designed to compute 7 well known screening variables. The expected use would be typically a public officer involved in making decisions during the contract award process. The chatbot provides a seamless tool for calculating in a simple way the screening variables. The goal is to increase operational efficiency and improve the quality of analyses carried out by specialists, highlighting the transformative potential of artificial intelligence in this field.

2. Methodology

The methodology adopted in this study is structured around two fundamental pillars: the identification of key statistical variables relevant to public procurement processes, and the conceptual design of an intelligent system capable of automating the analytical evaluation of tender data through natural language interaction. Each of these components is described below.

2.1 Selection of Relevant Variables for Tender Analysis

The first step involved the identification and selection of statistical variables with the potential to reveal significant insights into the competitiveness, consistency, and potential irregularities within public procurement procedures. This variable screening process was guided by both statistical criteria and practical considerations drawn from real-world procurement contexts.

In this work, the selection of screen variables have been taken from Imhof previous study (Imhof, 2017). The selected variables were chosen based on their capacity to capture relevant

patterns in the behaviour of submitted economic bids. Because each screen captures a different aspect of the distribution of bids, the combined use of different screens potentially allows accounting for different types of bid manipulation. The following is a brief description of the core metrics considered:

- Coefficient of Variation (CV): measures the relative dispersion of economic offers in relation to their mean. A high CV may indicate substantial heterogeneity among bids, potentially reflecting market uncertainty or a lack of clear evaluation criteria.
- Spread Inside Tender (SPD): quantifies the difference between the most extreme bids within a single tender. This helps the detection of unusually high or low offers that deviate significantly from the general distribution.
- Percentage Difference Between the Two Lowest Bids (DIFFP): assesses the relative gap between the lowest and second-lowest offers. A narrow difference may suggest high competition, while a large gap could raise concerns about the competitiveness of the process.
- Relative Distance (RD): represents the gap between the winning bid and the second-best offer, normalized by the overall variability of all bids. It provides a contextualized metric of competitive advantage.
- Kurtosis and Skewness: these indicators evaluate the shape of the bid distribution. Kurtosis measures the concentration of values around the mean, while skewness indicates asymmetry in the distribution, revealing potential outliers or bidding trends.
- Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KSTEST): this statistical test is used to determine whether the bid distribution follows a uniform pattern. Significant deviations may point to non-competitive behaviour or bid clustering.

These variables form the analytical core of the proposed system. Their selection is intended to equip the intelligent agent with the ability to interpret tender data in a technical, objective, and automated manner, thereby enhancing decision-making processes in public procurement. The formulation of each one is summarized in the next table, where sd_t is the (economic) bids standard deviation in auction t ; \bar{b}_t the mean (average) of all bids submitted to auction t ; $b_{max,t}$ the maximum (most expensive) bid; $b_{min,t}$ the minimum (lowest, cheapest) bid; b_{2t} is the second-lowest bid; $sd_{losingbids,t}$ is the standard deviation of the non-awarded bids (all but the winning bid); n_t is the number of bids submitted to auction t ; and b_{it} is the i -th bid in auction t when ordered from lowest to highest.

Table 1 Screening variables formulation.

Screen variable	Formulation
Coefficient of Variation	$CV_t = \frac{sd_t}{\bar{b}_t}$
Spread Inside Tender	$SPD_t = \frac{b_{max,t} - b_{min,t}}{b_{min,t}}$
Percentage Difference Between the Two Lowest Bids	$DIFFP_t = \frac{b_{2t} - b_{min,t}}{b_{min,t}}$
Relative Distance	$RD_t = \frac{b_{2t} - b_{min,t}}{sd_{losingbids,t}}$
Kurtosis	$KURT_t = \frac{n_t(n_t + 1)}{(n_t - 1)(n_t - 2)(n_t - 3)} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \left(\frac{b_{it} - \bar{b}_t}{sd_t} \right)^4 - \frac{3(n_t - 1)^3}{(n_t - 2)(n_t - 3)}$

Skewness

$$SKEW_t = \frac{n_t}{(n_t - 1)(n_t - 2)} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \left(\frac{b_{it} - \bar{b}_t}{sd_t} \right)^3$$

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

$$KSTEST_t = \max(D_t^+, D_t^-); D_t^+ = \max_i \left(\frac{b_{it}}{sd_t} - \frac{i_t}{n_t + 1} \right), D_t^- \\ = \max_i \left(\frac{i_t}{n_t + 1} - \frac{b_{it}}{sd_t} \right)$$

2.2 Conceptual Design of the Intelligent System

The second methodological axis focuses on the conceptual architecture of the intelligent agent designed to automate and enhance the analysis of public tenders. The proposed system is conceived as a conversational assistant capable of interacting with users in natural language, interpreting their queries, and delivering responses grounded in rigorous statistical analysis. It is intended not only to automate routine evaluations but also to assist in complex decision-making processes by contextualizing quantitative results within the specific logic of public procurement.

At a conceptual level, the system is composed of four main functional components that operate in a coordinated manner:

- **Natural Language Model:** this forms the interpretive core of the system. It is responsible for understanding user inputs, often expressed in informal or domain-specific language, and translating them into concrete analytical tasks. In doing so, it acts as a semantic bridge between the user's intention and the system's computational logic. Once the relevant analyses are executed, the model synthesizes the results into structured, coherent, and context-aware responses.
- **Analytical Tools Module:** this component includes a set of purpose-built tools specifically designed to compute the statistical screening metrics described in the previous section. These tools do not operate in isolation but rather are dynamically activated in response to the user's queries. For instance, when a user asks about bid dispersion, the agent triggers the appropriate tool to calculate the Coefficient of Variation (CV); if the user asks whether the distribution is uniform, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is applied. The tools are modular, scalable, and capable of producing precise numerical results adapted to each tender's context.
- **Decision Logic and Orchestration Module:** serving as the internal coordinator, this module manages the dialogue flow between the natural language model and the analytical tools. It interprets both the structure and semantic intent of each user prompt to determine which statistical procedures should be executed, when they should be applied, and how the outputs should be handled. This orchestration mechanism is what allows the system to function not as a static calculator, but as a responsive analytical agent capable of selecting and applying the appropriate screening logic on demand.
- **User Interface Layer:** the interface acts as the user's main point of interaction with the system. Designed for clarity and ease of use, it allows users to input relevant data, formulate analytical questions, and receive interpretable outputs without requiring any technical expertise. The interface also ensures traceability and auditability by providing access to past queries, results, and data inputs, essential features in public administration settings.

In essence, this conceptual architecture enables the agent to operate as a statistical evaluator-on-demand, capable of performing relevant screening analyses based on the user's natural language requests. Through this dynamic interaction, the system not only automates technical computations, but also interprets and explains the outcomes within the decision-making framework of public procurement.

By reducing the cognitive and technical burden associated with statistical evaluation, the agent supports more efficient and transparent procurement processes. The specific technologies, integration strategies, and deployment details used to implement this conceptual design are presented in the next section.

3. Results

This section presents the results obtained from the practical implementation of the intelligent agent designed to support the analysis of public tenders. It provides a detailed description of the technological choices made, the system architecture developed, and the performance of the agent across a variety of use cases. Emphasis is placed on the operational viability of the solution and the interpretability of the outputs.

3.1 Language Model Selection and Deployment Strategy

Following a comprehensive comparative evaluation of several advanced language models, including GPT-4, LLaMA, and Mistral, the Mistral 7B model was selected as the most suitable foundation for the intelligent agent. This decision was informed by a multidimensional analysis of four critical criteria: linguistic performance, computational efficiency, operational scalability, and compliance with data confidentiality requirements specific to public sector environments.

Mistral 7B (Mistral AI, n.d.) is a Transformer-based generative language model that leverages a 7-billion parameter architecture, offering a favourable trade-off between expressive power and resource requirements. Unlike larger models, which often require cloud-based infrastructure and GPU clusters, Mistral 7B is lightweight enough to be executed on-premises using local computing resources, without significant compromise in output quality, particularly when processing administrative, legal, or technical language associated with public tenders.

To meet stringent data privacy and sovereignty standards, particularly relevant in government-related workflows, the model was deployed using Ollama (Ollama, n.d.), a secure and efficient runtime environment for locally executing large language models. Ollama provides a containerized architecture that guarantees that no data leaves the internal network, thereby aligning with institutional security policies and ensuring full compliance with GDPR and national procurement data protection regulations.

Beyond data confidentiality, Ollama also offers fine-grained control over model behaviour. For the use case at hand, the generation temperature was set to 0.0, effectively disabling randomness in text generation. This deterministic setup ensures that analytical queries yield consistent, reproducible outputs, critical in institutional decision-making contexts. Additionally, configuration options related to context window size, token management, and caching strategies were optimized to support real-time responsiveness, even when processing large sets of input data or performing sequential analyses across multiple tenders.

This local deployment strategy proved fundamental not only for privacy and reproducibility, but also for latency reduction and system autonomy, making the agent viable even in environments with limited or regulated internet access.

3.2 Architecture and Tool Integration Using LangChain

The intelligent agent's architecture was designed with modularity, autonomy, and scalability in mind. At the heart of this architecture lies the LangChain framework (LangChain, n.d.), which provides a high-level abstraction for combining large language models with external tools in a flexible and task-aware environment. LangChain was selected due to its ability to integrate tool-based reasoning, query parsing, and contextual memory, all of which are essential for building robust, multi-step reasoning agents.

To enable autonomous task execution, the architecture is structured around the Structured Chat Zero-Shot ReAct paradigm (LangChain Blog, 2023) (Yao et al., 2023). This strategy empowers the language model to decide independently, based on the user's natural language query, whether and when to invoke external tools. Instead of relying on pre-defined flows or templates, the model interprets the intent of the query, evaluates the analytical needs, and dynamically selects the appropriate statistical operation or tool.

Within this architecture, several custom-developed analytical tools were modularly integrated and exposed to the agent as callable components:

- A symbolic and numerical computation module, based on SymPy (SymPy, n.d.), handles complex arithmetic and algebraic expressions. It supports evaluations such as price thresholds, normalized deviations, and value transformations that go beyond standard numerical operations, ensuring accurate mathematical processing even in symbolic terms.
- A suite of statistical analysis tools, implemented using NumPy (NumPy, n.d.) and SciPy (SciPy, n.d.), computes the core variables defined during the methodological phase. These include:
 - Coefficient of Variation (CV): for assessing relative dispersion in bidding behavior.
 - Spread Inside Tender (SPD): to measure the range between the most divergent offers.
 - DIFFP: for analyzing the percentage gap between the two lowest bids.
 - Relative Distance (RD): as a measure of winner advantage relative to bid distribution.
 - Kurtosis and Skewness: for evaluating the shape and symmetry of the distribution.
 - Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KSTEST): to statistically validate the uniformity of bid distributions.

All tools were developed as stateless, modular functions, designed to be executed on-demand. This ensures that each analysis is independent, reproducible, and not influenced by prior interactions, preserving consistency across sessions and users.

Once a tool is activated and a result is generated, the language model assumes responsibility for interpreting the outcome. It translates raw numerical outputs into natural language explanations that are both technically rigorous and contextually aligned with public procurement logic.

This layered architecture, combining autonomous reasoning, targeted computation, and contextual interpretation, enables the agent to perform complex multi-step analyses while maintaining the fluid, intuitive interaction style of a conversational assistant. The result is a robust yet user-friendly system that bridges the gap between statistical rigor and operational usability in public sector contexts.

3.3 User Interface Implementation with Streamlit

To ensure broad accessibility and ease of use, the intelligent agent was deployed through a web-based interface developed using Streamlit (Streamlit, 2021). This open-source framework was selected for its capacity to create interactive, real-time applications with minimal development overhead, making it well-suited for prototyping and deploying data-driven tools in institutional environments.

The user interface plays a crucial role in translating the system's advanced analytical capabilities into a usable and approachable experience for a diverse audience, including procurement officers, technical reviewers, and administrative staff with varying levels of technical expertise.

At a functional level, the interface supports the following core features:

- **Natural Language Interaction:** users can submit analytical queries using unrestricted, natural language without requiring knowledge of specific commands or statistical terminology. The system interprets the semantic intent of each query, identifies the appropriate analytical task, and delivers a coherent response articulated in natural language.
- **Dynamic Response Generation:** once a query is submitted, the agent processes it through the underlying architecture (described in previous sections), activating the relevant analytical tools, and returning results in a structured format. Each response includes not only the computed values but also an interpretation contextualized within the procurement framework.
- **Result Traceability and History:** the interface maintains a session-based log of all queries and generated responses. This feature supports transparency, allows users to track the evolution of their analyses and compare results across different tenders when needed.

In terms of usability, the interface was designed to minimize friction and cognitive load. It adopts a clean and responsive layout, with clear sections for data input, question formulation, and result presentation. Interactive components such as collapsible panels, progress indicators, and input validation feedback ensure a smooth experience, even for non-technical users.

The choice of Streamlit also facilitated rapid iteration and deployment, allowing continuous updates to both analytical logic and user experience based on testing and user feedback. Moreover, its compatibility with local and cloud-based environments ensures flexibility in deployment strategies, whether in secure intranet settings or broader institutional infrastructures.

Ultimately, the interface acts as the critical touchpoint between the user and the system's underlying analytical engine. By abstracting away technical complexity and offering intuitive interaction mechanisms, it empowers users to harness the full potential of the agent's analytical capabilities, contributing to more informed, transparent, and data-driven procurement evaluations. Figure 1 summarizes the interactions between the main components of the system.

Figure 1: System architecture.

3.4 Prompt-Based Testing and Functional Demonstration

To evaluate the practical performance of the intelligent agent and illustrate its real-world applicability, a series of prompt-based tests were conducted using the implemented interface. These tests aimed to simulate realistic use cases encountered by procurement analysts and assess the agent's ability to interpret, calculate, and explain results in a coherent and context-aware manner.

Each test involved submitting a natural language query related to one or more statistical dimensions of a given tender, using actual or simulated bid datasets. The system was evaluated based on its ability to:

- Correctly interpret the user's intent.
- Select the appropriate statistical tools.
- Execute the necessary calculations.
- Generate an accurate and meaningful explanation.
- Present the response in a clear and accessible format through the user interface.

The prompts varied in tone and structure to evaluate the model's adaptability. To provide a structured overview of the agent's performance, the following tables group a selection of representative queries by the statistical tool that the model successfully invoked. For each case, the prompt was formulated in natural language without explicit mention of the tool, allowing the agent to autonomously interpret the intent and respond accordingly.

Table 2: Coefficient of variation (CV).

Prompt	Agent Response
Could you calculate the coefficient of variation for these bids: 200, 220, 210, 190, 230?	The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is 0.0753.
I have a standard deviation of 15.2 and a mean of 100. What is the CV?	The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is 0.1520.

Table 3: Spread Inside Tender (SPD).

Prompt	Agent Response
What is the spread inside tender (SPD) for the following bids: 130, 145, 135, 125, 140?	The spread inside tender (SPD) for the given bids is 0.1600. In other words, the difference between the highest and lowest bid in this tender is 20 units (145 - 125).
Calculate the SPD when the minimum bid is 0 and the maximum is 100.	Cannot compute SPD when the minimum bid is 0.

Table 4: Difference between Two Lowest Bids (DIFFP).

Prompt	Agent Response
Among the bids 150, 140, 135, 120, and 125, what is the relative difference between the two lowest ones?	The DIFFP value is 0.0417.

Table 5: Relative Distance (RD).

Prompt	Agent Response
What is the kurtosis of the bids 100, 110, 95, 120, and 105?	Excess kurtosis is -0.0219. Mean: 106. Std Dev: 9.6177.

Table 6: Skewness (SKEW).

Prompt	Agent Response
Give me the skewness of the distribution of bids: 80, 150, 90, 200, 85.	The skewness of the bid distribution is 1.0721.

Table 7: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KSTEST).

Prompt	Agent Response
Do these bids follow a uniform distribution according to the KS test? 100, 110, 95, 120, 105.	The bids follow a uniform distribution according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (KSTEST).

Table 8: Calculator (General Math).

Prompt	Agent Response
I need to know what 8 squared is.	The result of the calculation is 64.

3.5 Agent Interaction and User Interface Overview

This section presents how users interact with the intelligent agent through a streamlined web interface, and how the system interprets, processes, and responds to natural language prompts in real time.

The user workflow is entirely conversational: users formulate questions in natural language, such as requests to analyze variability, identify distribution patterns, or compute derived indicators, and the system automatically identifies the appropriate tool, executes the calculation, and returns both the result and its interpretation.

The examples illustrate different types of user queries and the agent's corresponding behaviour, including:

- Interpreting the user's intent from domain-specific language,
- Automatically selecting the appropriate statistical or mathematical tool,
- Executing the calculation in real time,
- Returning a clear and concise response with domain-relevant insights.

These visual outputs confirm that the system can handle a variety of input formats and screening scenarios with robustness and contextual awareness.

- Figure 2. The user is welcomed by a streamlined layout and prompted to submit questions in natural language. The description highlights the agent's specialization in bidding-related statistical indicators, preparing the user for domain-specific interactions.
- Figure 3. The user submits a natural-language prompt with bid values, and the agent correctly identifies the intent, invokes the appropriate tool, and returns an accurate statistical result with a clear response.
- Figure 4. The agent processes a sequence of distinct queries involving variation, difference, kurtosis, and a general mathematical operation. This demonstrates its ability to understand diverse prompts, switch between tools, and maintain contextual coherence across interactions, keeping the references made in previous interactions.

Figure 2: Initial view of the agent interface.

Figure 3: Example interaction showing coefficient of variation calculation.

Figure 4: Multi-turn interaction with dynamic tool selection.

The screenshots serve as proof of the agent's functional correctness and its suitability for real-world analytical tasks in procurement contexts. Beyond showcasing accuracy in tool invocation and result generation, the examples highlight the agent's ability to adapt to natural, domain-specific language and provide interpretive responses that go beyond raw numbers.

4. Conclusions

This work presented the design, implementation, and evaluation of an intelligent conversational agent capable of performing advanced statistical and mathematical analyses applied to public procurement data. By leveraging modern natural language processing technologies and integrating structured tool-based reasoning, the agent was built to serve as a practical support system for analysts engaged in detecting irregularities or patterns in tendering processes.

The main achievements of this project can be summarized as follows:

- A modular agent architecture was developed using LangChain, with integrated support for both general-purpose mathematical reasoning and domain-specific statistical screening tools tailored to procurement analysis.
- The system was connected to a local language model (Mistral via Ollama), ensuring full offline operability, cost-free execution and high response speed without dependence on third-party APIs.
- A set of screening indicators, commonly used in collusion detection literature (CV, SPD, DIFFP, RD, KURT, SKEW and KSTEST), was implemented as callable tools. These tools were accessible through natural language interaction and automatically invoked by the agent based on the user's query intent.
- A chat-based user interface was built using Streamlit, allowing intuitive, human-friendly interactions with the real-time interpretation of queries, calculations and statistical outputs.

From the conducted prompt-based testing, the agent demonstrated a high level of robustness in understanding varying question formats, correctly selecting the relevant statistical method, and producing accurate results. Notably, the integration of interpretative layers in each response significantly enhanced the usefulness of outputs for non-technical users.

However, some limitations were identified:

- The first in each session occasionally exhibited inconsistent behaviour, likely due to model initialization or context management issues.
- Some edge cases, such as malformed inputs or ambiguous phrasing, still require improved error handling and fallback strategies.
- While the agent excels in descriptive analysis, it does not yet incorporate predictive modelling or anomaly detection, which could be valuable for future iterations.

This intelligent agent showcases the powerful synergy between natural language interfaces and statistical computing within a procurement-specific context. Its ability to understand user queries, select appropriate analytical methods, and return numerical results positions it as a practical and innovative tool for procurement analysis.

Beyond its functional capabilities, the project highlights how domain-specific tool integration, paired with accessible interfaces, can bridge the gap between complex statistical concepts and day-to-day decision-making in public administration. The architecture designed, modular, offline-capable, and highly customizable, offers a scalable foundation for extending this approach to other analytical domains.

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Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence

AI tools were used in the preparation of this work to support translation and improve language.

Communication aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals

